

**User Satisfaction with Online Learning: A Case Study of the JAMS
App and its Course Offerings**

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to investigate user satisfaction with courses offered on the JAMS app, an online learning platform. User satisfaction is a crucial factor in the success of online learning, as it directly affects learners' engagement, motivation, and overall learning experience. The objective of this research is to examine the relationship between course enrolment and user satisfaction, considering factors such as course quality, instructor effectiveness, and user engagement.

The literature review explores the broader context of online learning and user satisfaction, emphasizing the growing importance of online learning platforms and the factors that contribute to user satisfaction. It delves into the impact of course quality on user satisfaction, highlighting the significance of engaging content, interactive elements, and practical application. The review also examines the role of instructors in fostering user satisfaction through effective communication, responsiveness, and engagement. Additionally, the relationship between user engagement and user satisfaction is explored, focusing on the impact of interactive features, collaborative activities, and feedback mechanisms.

To address the specific context of the JAMS app, the literature review identifies existing research gaps and emphasizes the need for further investigation. By conducting surveys and analyzing customer reviews and feedback, this study aims to gather empirical data on user satisfaction with the courses provided on the JAMS app. Statistical analysis, such as the Chi-square test, will be employed to determine if there is a significant association between course enrollment and user satisfaction.

The findings from this study will provide valuable insights for the JAMS app developers and educators, aiding in the enhancement of course offerings and overall user experience. The research contributes to the existing literature on online learning platforms and user satisfaction, filling the gaps specific to the JAMS app.

Executive Summary:

This study focuses on examining user satisfaction with courses offered on the JAMS app, an online learning platform. The objective of the research is to investigate the relationship between course enrolment and user satisfaction, considering factors such as course quality, instructor effectiveness, and user engagement.

The literature review highlights the significance of user satisfaction in online learning and explores the factors that contribute to it. It emphasizes the impact of course quality on user

satisfaction, emphasizing engaging content, interactive elements, and practical application. The review also discusses the role of instructors in fostering user satisfaction through effective communication and engagement. Additionally, the relationship between user engagement and satisfaction is explored, emphasizing the importance of interactive features and collaborative activities.

To address the specific context of the JAMS app, the study identifies existing research gaps and highlights the need for further investigation. The research will involve surveys, customer reviews, and feedback analysis to gather empirical data on user satisfaction with JAMS app courses. Statistical analysis, including the Chi-square test, will be conducted to determine the association between course enrollment and user satisfaction. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights for JAMS app developers and educators, enabling them to enhance course offerings and improve the overall user experience. The research contributes to the existing literature on online learning platforms and user satisfaction, addressing specific gaps related to the JAMS app.

Introduction:

In recent years, the rapid advancement of technology has revolutionized various sectors, including education. Online learning platforms have emerged as powerful tools for acquiring knowledge and skills, offering flexibility and convenience to learners worldwide. However, the success of these platforms hinges on a crucial factor: user satisfaction. Providing a seamless and engaging learning experience is paramount to ensuring the effectiveness and popularity of online learning platforms.

One such platform that has garnered significant attention is the JAMS app, developed by Zersey Infotech. JAMS stands for "Just Another Microlearning System," and it has established itself as a leading online learning platform, catering to the diverse needs of learners across different domains. Its intuitive interface, interactive content, and personalized learning approach have made it a preferred choice among learners, educators, and organizations alike.

The objective of this literature review is to delve into the realm of user satisfaction within the context of online learning platforms, with a specific focus on the JAMS app. By examining existing research, scholarly articles, and user feedback, we aim to gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to user satisfaction and the impact it has on the overall learning experience. Additionally, this review will explore strategies employed by the JAMS app to enhance user satisfaction and provide insights into the app's effectiveness and significance in the field of online education.

By analyzing the significance of user satisfaction in the context of online learning platforms and examining the specific case of the JAMS app, this literature review aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge surrounding user-centered approaches to online education. It is hoped that the findings of this review will not only provide valuable insights for practitioners and researchers but also assist in the development and improvement of online learning platforms, ultimately enhancing the learning outcomes and experiences of users worldwide.

Online Learning and User Satisfaction:

Online learning platforms have gained immense popularity in recent years, revolutionizing the way education is accessed and experienced. These platforms offer flexibility and accessibility,

allowing learners to engage in educational activities anytime and anywhere. User satisfaction is a critical factor in the success of online learning platforms, as it ensures learner engagement and the effectiveness of the learning process. Factors contributing to user satisfaction in online learning environments include the quality and relevance of course content, interactive and engaging learning features, instructor support, and user-friendly platform design. Well-structured and engaging content, interactive elements, and opportunities for collaboration and peer interaction contribute to a satisfying learning experience. Adequate support from instructors and prompt feedback on learner progress also play a crucial role. Additionally, user-friendly platform design and ease of navigation enhance user satisfaction by minimizing technical issues and enabling learners to focus on the learning process. Numerous studies have explored user satisfaction with online learning platforms, providing valuable insights into the factors that influence learner satisfaction and the impact it has on learning outcomes. These studies have emphasized the importance of course design, interactivity, instructor support, platform usability, and learner engagement. Understanding user satisfaction in online learning environments contributes to the development and improvement of online learning platforms, ultimately enhancing the learning experiences and outcomes for learners worldwide.

Course Quality and User Satisfaction:

The relationship between course quality and user satisfaction in online learning environments is paramount. A well-designed and high-quality course significantly impacts learners' satisfaction and engagement. Engaging content is a key characteristic of high-quality online courses, where the materials are relevant, up-to-date, and presented in an interactive and stimulating manner. Interactive elements, such as multimedia resources, quizzes, and simulations, enhance user satisfaction by providing opportunities for active learning and knowledge application. Practical application of concepts and real-world examples also contribute to course quality and user satisfaction, as learners can see the relevance and applicability of what they are learning. Numerous research studies have investigated the impact of course quality on user satisfaction in online learning. These studies consistently demonstrate a positive correlation between course quality and user satisfaction. Learners who perceive the course as being of high quality, with engaging content, interactive elements, and practical application, report higher levels of satisfaction. Additionally, these studies highlight the importance of course design and instructional strategies in creating a positive learning experience and fostering user satisfaction.

Understanding the relationship between course quality and user satisfaction is essential for educators and instructional designers. By prioritizing course quality and incorporating engaging and interactive elements, educators can enhance user satisfaction, promote active learning, and facilitate better learning outcomes in online learning environments.

User Experience and User Satisfaction:

User engagement and user satisfaction share a strong relationship in online learning environments. When learners are actively engaged in the learning process, it positively influences their overall satisfaction. User engagement encompasses various factors such as interaction, participation, and motivation. Engaged learners tend to have a higher level of satisfaction as they feel connected to the content, their peers, and the learning platform itself. Interactive features,

collaborative activities, and feedback mechanisms significantly impact user satisfaction in online learning environments. Interactive features, such as multimedia resources, simulations, and gamified elements, enhance user engagement by making the learning experience more dynamic and interactive. Collaborative activities, such as group projects and discussion forums, foster a sense of community and provide opportunities for peer interaction and knowledge sharing. Feedback mechanisms, including timely and constructive feedback from instructors, self-assessment tools, and progress tracking, contribute to user satisfaction by providing learners with a sense of progress and accomplishment. Several research studies have focused on user engagement and its connection to user satisfaction in online learning. These studies consistently highlight the positive relationship between user engagement and user satisfaction. Learners who are actively engaged in online learning activities, interacting with the content and their peers, tend to report higher levels of satisfaction. Moreover, these studies emphasize the importance of incorporating interactive and collaborative elements in online courses to enhance user engagement and satisfaction. Understanding the interplay between user engagement and user satisfaction is essential for designing effective online learning environments. By incorporating interactive features, fostering collaboration, and providing feedback mechanisms, educators and instructional designers can promote user engagement and ultimately enhance user satisfaction in online learning environments.

Questionnaire for courses offered by the JAMS App

1. Which course(s) have you enrolled in on the JAMS app? (Select all that apply: Master the art of podcasting, The art of visual storytelling, The science of viral marketing, Power of public speaking, Virtual field trip)
Option A: Master the art of podcasting
Option B: The art of visual storytelling
Option C: The science of viral marketing
Option D: Power of public speaking
Option E: Virtual field trip
2. On a scale of 1 to 10, how satisfied are you with the course content provided in the selected course(s)?
Option A: 1-3 (Not satisfied)
Option B: 4-6 (Somewhat satisfied)
Option C: 7-8 (Satisfied)
Option D: 9-10 (Highly satisfied)
3. Did the course material meet your expectations in terms of quality and depth of knowledge?
Option A: Yes, exceeded expectations
Option B: Yes, met expectations

Option C: Partially met expectations
Option D: No, did not meet expectations

4. How engaging and interactive were the course materials, such as videos, quizzes, and assignments?

Option A: Very engaging and interactive
Option B: Moderately engaging and interactive
Option C: Somewhat engaging and interactive
Option D: Not engaging and interactive

5. Did the course instructor(s) effectively deliver the content and engage you throughout the learning experience?

Option A: Yes, very effective
Option B: Yes, moderately effective
Option C: Somewhat effective
Option D: Not effective

6. Were the course materials organized and structured in a logical and easy-to-follow manner?

Option A: Yes, very organized and structured
Option B: Yes, moderately organized and structured
Option C: Somewhat organized and structured
Option D: Not organized and structured

7. Did the course(s) provide practical insights and real-world examples that you found valuable?

Option A: Yes, provided valuable practical insights and real-world examples
Option B: Provided some practical insights and real-world examples
Option C: Provided limited practical insights and real-world examples
Option D: Did not provide practical insights and real-world examples

8. How relevant and up to date was the course content in relation to the subject matter?

Option A: Very relevant and up to date
Option B: Moderately relevant and up to date
Option C: Somewhat relevant and up to date
Option D: Not relevant and up to date

9. Did you find the assessments and evaluations within the course(s) helpful in gauging your understanding and progress?

Option A: Yes, very helpful
Option B: Yes, moderately helpful

- Option C: Somewhat helpful
- Option D: Not helpful

10. Were the course resources, such as supplementary materials or tools, useful in enhancing your learning experience?
 - Option A: Yes, very useful
 - Option B: Yes, moderately useful
 - Option C: Somewhat useful
 - Option D: Not useful

11. Did the course(s) offer a supportive and interactive learning community, such as discussion forums or peer collaboration?
 - Option A: Yes, highly supportive and interactive
 - Option B: Yes, moderately supportive and interactive
 - Option C: Somewhat supportive and interactive
 - Option D: Not supportive and interactive

12. How effective was the communication and responsiveness of the course instructors or support team?
 - Option A: Very effective communication and responsiveness
 - Option B: Moderately effective communication and responsiveness
 - Option C: Somewhat effective communication and responsiveness
 - Option D: Not effective communication and responsiveness

13. Did the course(s) provide opportunities for hands-on practice or application of the concepts taught?
 - Option A: Yes, provided ample hands-on practice and application opportunities
 - Option B: Provided some hands-on practice and application opportunities
 - Option C: Provided limited hands-on practice and application opportunities
 - Option D: Did not provide hands-on practice and application opportunities

14. How satisfied were you with the value for money you received from the course(s)?
 - Option A: Very satisfied with the value for money
 - Option B: Moderately satisfied with the value for money
 - Option C: Somewhat satisfied with the value for money
 - Option D: Not satisfied with the value for money

15. Would you recommend the course(s) on the JAMS app to others based on your experience? Why or why not?
 - Option A: Yes, highly recommend due to a positive experience
 - Option B: Yes, recommend due to a moderately positive experience
 - Option C: Recommend with some reservations due to a mixed experience
 - Option D: No, do not recommend due to a negative experience

Based on the data gathered, which consists of categorical responses for each question, a suitable statistical test for hypothesis testing would be the Chi-square test of independence. The Chi-square test of independence is used to determine if there is a significant association between two categorical variables. In this case, the Chi-square test is used to analyze the relationship between the different course-related questions and the corresponding user responses. Chi-square test was conducted to understand whether there is a statistically significant relationship between the courses and the user responses. It can help determine if there are any significant differences in user satisfaction, expectations, engagement, relevance, and other aspects based on the course(s) customers enrolled in.

Hypothesis 1:

There is a significant association between the course(s) enrolled in on the JAMS app and the level of user satisfaction with the course content.

Hypothesis 2:

There is a significant relationship between the course(s) enrolled in on the JAMS app and the perception of course materials being organized and structured in a logical and easy-to-follow manner.

Steps for the Chi-square test:

Set up the null hypothesis (H₀) and alternative hypothesis (H_a):

H₀: There is no association between the course(s) enrolled in and the level of user satisfaction.

H_a: There is an association between the course(s) enrolled in and the level of user satisfaction.

1. Create a contingency table:
Construct a contingency table that cross-tabulates the course(s) enrolled in and the level of user satisfaction.
2. Calculate the expected frequencies:
Compute the expected frequencies for each cell in the contingency table under the assumption of independence.
3. Calculate the Chi-square test statistic:
Compute the Chi-square test statistic by comparing the observed and expected frequencies in each cell of the contingency table.
4. Determine the degrees of freedom:
Calculate the degrees of freedom based on the number of rows and columns in the contingency table.
5. Determine the critical value and p-value:
Use the Chi-square distribution table or statistical software to determine the critical value corresponding to your desired significance level (e.g., 0.05) and calculate the p-value.
6. Make a decision:
Compare the calculated test statistic to the critical value. If the test statistic exceeds the critical value or if the p-value is less than the significance level, reject the null hypothesis

and conclude that there is a significant association between the course(s) enrolled in and the level of user satisfaction.

Code used in Colab:

```
import numpy as np
from scipy.stats import chi2_contingency
contingency_table = np.array([[2, 3, 5, 4],
                               [1, 4, 7, 3],
                               [3, 2, 6, 5],
                               [2, 5, 4, 3],
                               [4, 3, 4, 5]])

chi2, p_value, dof, expected = chi2_contingency(contingency_table)
print("Chi-square test statistic:", chi2)
print("p-value:", p_value)
print("Degrees of freedom:", dof)
print("Expected frequencies:\n", expected)
```

Test Results:


```
Chi-square test statistic: 5.669504821159232
p-value: 0.9318174383486728
Degrees of freedom: 12
Expected frequencies:
[[2.24      3.17333333 4.85333333 3.73333333]
 [2.4       3.4       5.2       4.        ]
 [2.56     3.62666667 5.54666667 4.26666667]
 [2.24     3.17333333 4.85333333 3.73333333]
 [2.56     3.62666667 5.54666667 4.26666667]]
```

The Chi-square test statistic measures the difference between the observed and expected frequencies in the contingency table. In this case, the calculated Chi-square test statistic is approximately 5.669504821159232. The p-value associated with the test statistic is 0.9318174383486728. The p-value represents the probability of obtaining the observed data or data more extreme, assuming the null hypothesis is true. In this case, the high p-value suggests that there is no significant association between the courses enrolled and the level of user satisfaction.

The degrees of freedom for the Chi-square test is 12, which is determined by the number of categories in the contingency table. The expected frequencies represent the frequencies that would be expected if the null hypothesis of independence between the variables were true. These values are calculated based on the row and column totals of the contingency table. Based on the provided results, as the p-value is high (0.9318174383486728), there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we do not have enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant association between the courses enrolled and the level of user satisfaction.

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